

Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations

FISH4ACP

INVEST

Showcasing
returns on
investment
in aquatic
value chains

The Marshall Islands ENERGY AUDITS

The investment case for renewable
energies and infrastructure upgrades
in the Marshall Islands tuna sector

In partnership with

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FISH4ACP INVEST

A series of investment cases showing the return on investment in aquatic value chains in Africa, the Caribbean and the Pacific under the FISH4ACP programme.

“Energy is a real concern for our business. We are very excited by the investment solutions to lower our costs and reduce our carbon footprint.”

Jerry Kramer
 Chief Executive Officer,
 Pacific International, Inc.

ENERGY AUDITS

AT A GLANCE

- ➔ FISH4ACP-led energy audits of the onshore tuna industry in the Marshall Islands demonstrate that significant energy savings and carbon footprint reductions are possible by investing in renewable energy and infrastructure upgrades.
- ➔ The audits, covering the four major onshore companies, propose practical solutions that would result in cost savings on energy bills of 25–30 per cent.
- ➔ Investments identified range from USD 25 000 to USD 1 750 000 and have a short payback period of months to a few years, given the savings in energy costs.
- ➔ Reducing the carbon footprint of the onshore tuna industry by lowering diesel use and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions could be an extra incentive for investors or corporate donors managing carbon offset portfolios.
- ➔ Energy audits have huge potential to identify energy savings and carbon footprint reductions for other Small Island Developing States (SIDS) in the Pacific region with onshore tuna industries.

ENERGY AUDITS

THE ISSUE

Onshore fish processing companies in the Marshall Islands face high energy costs due to their remote location and increasing temperatures due to climate change.

A key challenge for the main tuna hub Majuro is to maintain a reliable power supply for tuna processing and support services. This is critical to ensure the quality of fish during processing, storage, containerization and export. Power breakdowns and operational delays put the profitability of the companies involved and the reputation of the Marshall Islands as a tuna hub at risk.

Given that the local electricity grid has limited capacity, and the energy provided is expensive and mainly caters for the needs of the local population, most companies rely on their own diesel-powered generators.

At around USD 3.00 per litre, using diesel to generate electricity costs between USD 0.75 and USD 0.95 per kWh, more than three times the rate in many developed countries. Total energy costs across four key shore-based companies exceed USD 6.5 million per year, primarily for cold storage, fishmeal production and container refrigeration.

The onshore fish processing and service support sector currently does not use any renewable energy, despite Majuro offering favourable conditions for wind power and solar energy, making the industry highly vulnerable to fuel price volatility and supply disruption.

THE ACTION

FISH4ACP audited four onshore companies as part of its efforts to strengthen the Marshall Islands as a hub for sustainable tuna landings.

- ➔ **Pan Pacific Foods (PPF)**
is a key employer providing over 250 jobs and engages in loining, cold storage, containerization and exports of tuna to canneries in other countries.
- ➔ **Pacific International Inc. (PII)**
owns and operates a private fishing dock, and provides vessel, net repair and containerization services.
- ➔ **The Majuro Stevedore & Terminal Company (MSTCO)**
operates Delap dock and a 400-square meter site dedicated to refrigerated containers for high-value tuna exports.
- ➔ **Marshall Islands Fishing Venture (MIFV)**
a longline fishing company with onshore fish processing facilities.

The audits assessed the plant, equipment, infrastructure and energy consumption of each company, while identifying practical solutions to reduce energy costs by optimizing systems or investing in new ones, envisaging the integration of renewable energy.

The investment costs for each solution were estimated, along with energy savings, and the payback period was calculated taking the energy efficiencies and associated cost savings into account.

The audits resulted in recommendations for costed infrastructure upgrades along with the associated energy savings. Given that companies may need additional resources to make investments, interventions could be considered for donor or external finance.

Fig. 3 Rendering of potential roof structures for harvesting solar energy.

Fig. 4 Diagram of a storage and workflow for a small scale slurry ice plant with horizontally tanked storage.

Some examples of the investments and the resulting benefits include:

- ➔ Construction of an open-sided shed with integrated solar roof panels to cover up to 100 stacked refrigerated containers. The structure would reduce the cooling load on refrigerated containers and extend container lifespan, while solar energy would decrease energy consumption, resulting in combined savings of 30 per cent. The structure would cost USD 1 750 000, with yearly cost savings of USD 1 250 000 and a payback period of just under 1.5 years.
- ➔ Thermal insulation, reflective roof panels and enhanced ventilation systems for a tuna processing hall would reduce solar heat transfer and prevent heat building up in the processing facility. Replacement of ageing compressors used for refrigeration would improve cooling speed, reduce runtime and lower diesel consumption by approximately 20 per cent. At a cost of USD 180 000, these interventions would generate annual energy savings of USD 225 000, with a payback period of under 10 months.
- ➔ Resurfacing a container yard with industrial-grade paving would lower the energy consumption of the lifters used to move containers by 20 per cent thanks to reduced 'rolling resistance' caused by uneven ground, puddles and loose substrate. It would also reduce lifter maintenance costs and downtime due to tyre damage and hydraulic failures, and lessen costs associated with emergency rental charges of USD 800 per hour when lifters are not operational. Investment costs for surface paving would be USD 1 750 000, with a payback period of less than a year.
- ➔ A new type of ice machine, capable of producing 12 metric tonnes of ice per day, would reduce energy consumption by up to 25 per cent compared to flake ice, while delivering faster chilling and improved product preservation. The cost would be USD 80 000 with a payback period of 2 years.

TRANSFERABILITY AND KEY LESSONS

The handling, processing and storage of tuna catch requires considerable levels of investment in shore-side infrastructure in the form of cold stores, chill rooms, processing facilities, dock-side offloading equipment, and containers.

The audits conducted in the Marshall Islands have huge potential for other tuna processing countries in the Pacific where annual catches of tuna of between 2.5 and 3 million tonnes are more than 50 per cent of the global landed volumes.

Key lessons relevant for the transfer to other locations:

- ➔ Investments in equipment and infrastructure can generate significant reductions in energy costs and can have short payback periods.
- ➔ Energy audits quantifying the cost of investments and energy savings, demonstrating a return on investment and a short payback period, can serve to prioritize investments and benefit managers and investors by presenting the business case for investments.
- ➔ Individual businesses may not have the capital to self-finance investments, so access to concessional loans, blended finance instruments, or grant mechanisms may be necessary.
- ➔ Reductions in energy consumption especially when switching to renewable energy, can help to generate funding and investments based on carbon offsetting, ESG principles and CSR goals.
- ➔ Temporary and modular solutions may support phased implementation, and shared infrastructure (including with the help of public-private partnerships [PPPs]) can reduce the financial burden on individual companies.

FISH4ACP: BRINGING MORE BENEFITS FROM TUNA INDUSTRY ONSHORE IN THE MARSHALL ISLANDS

LEARN MORE

In close collaboration with the Marshall Islands Marine Resources Authority, FISH4ACP is supporting the Marshall Islands to strengthen its position as a tuna hub in the Pacific with a view to generate an estimated USD 33 million of direct value added from purse seine tuna fishing in ten years' time, ensuring that 30 percent of tuna catches will be containerized.

With actors from across the value chain, as well as authorities and other partners, FISH4ACP is supporting the tuna purse seine value chain. FISH4ACP is implementing an upgrading strategy based on an in-depth analysis of the value chain. The strategy aims to bring more benefits onshore through an increase in landings of tuna, stimulating employment and boosting value addition.

WHAT WE FOCUS ON

- ➔ Increasing the added value of tuna fishing locally by increasing the volume of containerized catch.
- ➔ Improving tuna storage and sorting facilities by expanding cold storage capacity.
- ➔ Increasing tuna landings and exports through the establishment of a competent authority (CA).
- ➔ Improving social and environmental sustainability, promoting cultural and gender sensitivity and encouraging the use of renewable energy.

The energy audits are part of the last component of the upgrading strategy on sustainability.

PARTNERS

- European Union Delegation to the Pacific
- Koo's Fishing Company Limited (Koo's)
- Majuro Stevedore & Terminal Company (MSTCO)
- Marshall Islands Fishing Company (MIFCO)
- Marshall Islands Fishing Venture (MIFV)
- Marshall Islands Marine Resources Authority (MIMRA)
- Marshall Islands Port Authority
- Ministry of Natural Resources and Commerce
- Pacific International Inc. (PII)
- Pan Pacific Fishing Inc. & Pan Pacific Foods (PPF)
- Pacific Island Tuna Provisions LLC (PITP)

FISH4ACP INVESTMENT CASE

The Marshall Islands

ENERGY AUDITS

- ➔ Energy audits in four leading onshore tuna processing and handling companies.
- ➔ Company-specific investment solutions identified to save yearly energy costs of up to 25–30 per cent, equal to USD 1 625 000 – 1 950 000.
- ➔ Energy savings enable short payback periods on investments required ranging from USD 25 000 to USD 1 750 000.
- ➔ Great potential for audits in other small island development states in the Pacific region.

FISH4ACP AND THE MARSHALL ISLANDS TUNA PURSE SEINE VALUE CHAIN

- ➔ FISH4ACP is supporting the Marshall Islands to generate more added value by increasing tuna landings and improving the efficiency of tuna handling, processing and storage, including through energy audits.
- ➔ Majuro, capital of the Marshall Islands, is the world's busiest tuna transshipment port. From 2014–2019 an average of 315 000 tonnes of tuna were moved through Majuro each year to canneries in other countries.
- ➔ Around 15 000 tonnes of tuna is landed in the Marshall Islands, loaded into containers and shipped to canneries elsewhere.
- ➔ Marshall Islands-flagged purse seine vessels catch around 75 000 tonnes a year, valued at around USD 100 million.
- ➔ Onshore infrastructure in the Marshall Islands to handle landings, loining, containerisation, and vessel support services to fishing vessels is considerable.

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Contact:
Fisheries and Aquaculture –
Natural Resources and Sustainable
Production
FISH4ACP@fao.org
Food and Agriculture Organization
of the United Nations